

A DYNAMIC NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF AN UPPER HUMAN ARM MODEL FOR CUFF-BASED OSCILLOMETRIC BLOOD PRESSURE MEASUREMENT

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Introduction

Oscillometric blood pressure (BP) measurement is a widely used, non-invasive technique that determines the BP by analysing the arterial volume changes, which manifests as oscillations in response to the external pressure. Previous research [1] models this as a uniformly applied external pressure on the upper human arm to simulate the pressure oscillations of the artery. This investigation employs a more realistic approach to evaluating the effect of cuff buckling on artery lumen area changes when the external pressure is applied through the inflation and deflation phases of a cuff.

Methods

A human upper arm was modelled in ABAQUS®, using geometry from the literature [1], to simulate the pressure changes in the artery when an external pressure was applied through an air-filled cuff. Hyper-elastic material properties of the brachial artery were taken from Ref. [2]. The internal artery pressure was synchronized with the clinical pulse rate for a blood pressure of 110/70 mmHg. The transmission of cuff pressure through the soft tissue to the brachial artery was simulated, and the lumen area changes of the artery were determined. The cuff pressure was applied from 0 to 150 mmHg with linear dynamics inflation and deflation over 10 and 30 s, respectively. The arterial lumen area changes were tracked for the deflation cycle, and an oscillometric waveform was generated based on pressure changes in the brachial artery.

Results and Discussion

The buckling of the cuff during the inflation and deflation phases led to non-uniform pressure transmission to the artery, shown in Fig. 1(a). This non-uniformity created localised pressure variations in the soft tissue, Fig. 1(b). Consequently, the pressure transmission ratio decreased, leading to reduced arterial deformation, Fig. 1(c). The maximum amplitude of the oscillometric waveform on the pressure axis is Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP), as shown in Fig. 1(f).

The peak of the oscillometric waveform was shifted towards the right, for cuff-based pressure application compared to uniform external pressure as shown in Fig. 1(f). This shift towards higher pressure indicates that the MAP is overestimated due to the buckling of the cuff.

This study contradicts earlier findings [1], which reported the arterial volume and lumen area changes based on external pressure applied uniformly on the tissue without the cuff. The reduction in pressure transmission depends on the type and material of the cuff fabric. These findings signify the improvement in the design and calibration of blood pressure monitoring devices, ultimately enhancing their accuracy in clinical settings.

References

1. Lan, H., et al., *Effect of tissue mechanical properties on cuff-based blood pressure measurements*. Medical engineering & physics, 2011. **33**(10): p. 1287-1292.
2. Bank, A.J., et al., *In vivo human brachial artery elastic mechanics: effects of smooth muscle relaxation*. Circulation, 1999. **100**(1): p. 41-47.

Figure 1 Effect of cuff buckling on oscillometric blood pressure measurement, showing (a) cuff buckling; (b) pressure distribution in tissue; (c) cross-sectional pressure distribution; (d) arterial compression; (e) oscillometric waveform, and (f) shift in MAP with and without cuff.

